

USE OF TECHNOLOGY AND METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Madaminova Gulirano

Andijan state foreign languages institute, Faculty of English philology, teaching methodology and translation studies, 3rd year student

Madaminova Diyora

Andijan state foreign languages institute, Faculty of English philology, teaching methodology and translation studies, 3rd year student.

Annotation: The importance of learning and teaching foreign languages has substantially expanded in recent years. By employing a range of cutting edge tactics, procedures, and interactive games that test a wide range of students this is done to make foreign language education more entertaining. With these Students' interest in the subject is further increased via games throughout the lecture. In this article, approaches and procedures for learning languages are discussed.

Key words: modernizing world, field, cutting-edge pedagogical technology, interactive and inventive approaches, communication, video clip, demonstration, dialogue, CD player, the Internet, role-playing, action games, working in pairs, graphic organizer.

Science and technology are expanding quickly in the rapidly modernizing world of today. Every field is making progress. In particular, science is undergoing substantial development and advancement. One of the key components of modern education is the use of new, cutting edge pedagogical technology to teach each subject to pupils. The emphasis on teaching and learning foreign languages in our nation increased even more after the passage of the decision of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Abdug'aniyevich Karimov dated December 13, 2012 PQ 1875.

In our nation, the teaching of foreign languages has entered a new phase, a new period. During the course of foreign language classes, the use of cutting-edge pedagogical technology, interactive, inventive approaches, communicative, and informative instruments is essential. In our nation, new guidelines and standards for teaching foreign languages and evaluating the knowledge and abilities of foreign language teachers have been devised in accordance with the CEFR's recommendations. It claims that textbooks were written with general education and vocational college students in mind. These specifications led to the installation of stands and modern information and communication methods in classrooms.

Learning a foreign language is becoming more and more popular. Reading, speaking, hearing, and speaking are the four components of foreign language science, and distinct ideas and abilities are provided for each of them. Modern information technologies are effectively used in the educational process through educational technology. By incorporating cutting-edge, new technologies into the educational process, it also offers for improving the quality and effectiveness of instruction. Utilizing such information and communication technology in particular has a number of benefits for learning a foreign language. Modern technology plays an unparalleled role in both teaching and learning languages. Every facet of learning a foreign language benefits from the use of technology (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For instance, this procedure obviously requires a computer, player, and CDs in order to listen and understand. One of the most crucial aspects of language learning is listening comprehension. The reader must also focus on the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammar standards, and use of terminology and its meanings.

Students' knowledge of and proficiency with information and communication technologies is a key component in the usage of contemporary technologies in the educational process. One of the most effective methods is to use modern technology to teach and learn a foreign language. The student can watch and listen to foreign

language video clips, demonstrations, dialogues, movies, or cartoons while using a computer. They can also listen to and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs. A more traditional method is to use tape recorders and cassettes. Another option is to use CD players. For students, learning a foreign language is more engaging and effective when these technical tools are used. It is challenging to envision our lives in the age of globalization without the Internet. It is regarded as one of the most efficient ways to apply it when learning and instructing in a foreign language. Through the Internet, you will be able to communicate with others who are multilingual. The practice of composing letters via email can help your writing.

Using contemporary communication technology properly and strategically in the educational process is of utmost importance if one is to raise student interest in learning a foreign language and improve teaching efficiency. Through this, the chance to employ cutting-edge educational technology will be created, and demand will rise. Today's cutting-edge instructional technologies come in a variety of forms. The efficacy of the lesson will be high, and students' interest in the lesson will improve, if teachers cover the subject in their classes in a variety of ways. By integrating and applying innovations into the educational process, it aims to boost the efficacy of education. The interest in the lesson and language learning is increased when different role-playing and action games are used in foreign language sessions.

Working in pairs or small groups enables students to practice communication skills. One of the most crucial methods for illuminating the subject and presenting it to students in the educational process is through the use of graphic organizers. It is also feasible to address the same subject using a variety of visual organizers. It is appropriate to utilize graphic organizers when teaching a foreign language to clarify new terminology and grammatical rules associated with the subject. Additionally, if these are presented using graphic organizers, they will be simple to recall.

In the process of teaching a foreign language, employing various tables effectively is also very high. Students can learn a specific grammatical rule, such as how to create sentences using different tenses or where to place new words, by employing tables in the instructional process. Modern information technologies and cutting-edge educational technologies will be used effectively in the educational process at a time when there is a strong requirement to learn a foreign language. The proper and efficient use of cutting-edge educational tools is key to their success in the classroom.

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